

UDK 330

IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN FORMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ANNOTATION

In this article, modern forms of employment, remote employment, remote work, formation of a flexible virtual labor market, development of modern non-standard forms of employment, introduction of modern forms of employment in the digital economy and formation of an innovative system are proposed.

Keywords: *freelancer, outsourcing, online exchange, outstaffing, digital economy, digital industry, remote employment, flexible virtual labor market, informal employment.*

INTRODUCTION

With the development of information technologies, new directions of employment are emerging today. Employers are able to hire employees voluntarily and at will, and geographical location and time difference are irrelevant. Employees are able to perform their tasks remotely using information technologies, and are able to perform the assigned task at any time without leaving the house.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A number of scientists have conducted research on modern forms of employment, remote employment. Carl Schwab, the founder and president of the Davos Economic

Forum, argued that the main factor of production in the digital economy is still not capital, but human resources. creates¹[3].

Odegov Yu.G. and Pavlova, according to VVs "Based on the accumulated knowledge, today we are facing the disappearance of the difference and separation between industries, the integration of industries and the emergence of new professions, and this process is accelerating."²[2].

Academician QXAbdurakhmanov believes that "remote relations" between the employer and employees are a component of the process of decentralization of labor activity in time and space. This also serves to form a flexible virtual labor market." "Remote work (telework) is a labor activity performed at a distance from the employer with the help of information and communication technologies. The main feature of this form of employment is the establishment of virtual "economic relations at a distance" between the employer and the employee.³[4, pp. 324-325].

According to Zokirova NK, Abdurahmanova G., Sagidullin FR, "Technological progress and the transition to the information society require highly qualified and mobile, i.e., changes in the labor market require quickly flexible employees."⁴[5, p. 28].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the context of the development of the digital economy, one of the most important problems in the effective organization and management of labor activities is the issue of attracting qualified employees. Today, the rapid development of the

¹ https://www.oxfordmartin.ox.ac.uk/downloads/academic/The_Future_of_Employment.pdf.

² Odegov Yuri Gennadevich, Pavlova Valentina Vasilevna Novye tekhnologii i ix vliyanie na rynek truda // Uroven jizni naseleniya regionov Rossii. 2018. No. 2 (208). - S. 60-70.

³ Abdurahmanov K.Kh. Labor economics: theory and practice. Textbook. Revised and supplemented 3rd edition. T.: "FAN", 2019. p. 552.

⁴ Zokirova N.K., Abdurahmanova G., Sagidullin F.R. Transformation form zanyatosti v innovatsionnom razvitii // International scientific review. 2020. No. LXX. - S. 24-28.

globalization of the world economy and the possibility of using the Internet system on a large scale make it possible to solve this problem.

The development of the economy leads to the emergence of modern non-standard forms of employment:

- informal employment;
- virtual employment;
- part-time employment;
- self-employment;
- temporary unemployment [3].

With the development of information technologies, new directions of employment are emerging today. Employers are able to hire employees voluntarily and at will, regardless of geographic location or time. Employees are able to perform their tasks remotely using information technologies, and are able to perform the assigned task at any time without leaving the house.

In remote work, there are serious changes in the nature of the traditional workplace, the working hours, the location of the workplace, and the forms of payment for labor. In the digital economy, the meaning of unemployment is now fundamentally changing, because now, digital technologies are not distributing jobs, but labor tasks.

Digital technologies require the employee to take responsibility and independently perform work activities along with high skills and knowledge. Now the employee organizes his own work, the salary is paid via the Internet. External control of the employee's labor activity is carried out through data and reports without his involvement.

Also, the fact that serious changes are taking place in the field of employment in the context of the transition to the digital economy is proof that the demand for specialists with modern knowledge and skills is steadily increasing. There are also changes in employees' workplaces and working conditions. The transition to the digital economy leads to a change in the composition of employment, the effective use of the

intellectual potential of employees, and the expansion of the influence of factors that increase the efficiency of innovative processes. Integration processes and globalization, provision of labor market information,

In our country as well as in the world, it is suitable for innovative economy innovative riv of nat market the process of awakening is taking shape at This process is me introduce innovative forms and types of employment in the national market social-iq social, institutional aim improvement and promotion of sa success specific mechanism to make it necessary to format Meh in the innovative direction the development strategy of the nat market is a modern socioeconomic hodysey theory, he analysis from a practical and practical point of view hand organize systematization, employment from the work system, the quality indicators of its traditional directions defines new requirements that imply change.

Accordingly, in the context of the transition to the digital economy, taking into account the regional characteristics of the labor market development in Uzbekistan, it is of particular importance to introduce modern forms and types of employment and improve their institutional foundations.

In the context of the development of the digital economy, one of the most important problems in the effective organization and management of labor activities is the issue of attracting qualified employees. Currently, the industry has moved to the next stage of development, the economy is based on innovation, "In Industry-2" countries "The term "Ish-4" also appeared. "Work-4", i.e., working in the digital economy requires employees to improve their knowledge and skills throughout their lives, along with the most up-to-date knowledge and advanced skills.⁵

Now, the meaning of unemployment in the digital economy is fundamentally changing, because now, not jobs, but labor tasks are distributed through digital technologies. Remote employment is also undergoing significant changes in the nature of the traditional workplace. Studying the experience of developed countries, we can

⁵ https://www.bmas.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/PDFPublikationen/Forschungsberichte/forschungsberichte-fb-442-arbeitsqualitaet.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1

emphasize that one of the modern and promising forms of providing jobs to the population is home-based remote employment. The main advantage of freelancing, outsourcing and domestic work is its flexibility. Employees, regardless of the location of the enterprise, have the opportunity to organize work remotely based on mutual agreement (Figure 1).

1 - Picture. Remote employment organization system.

In our country, it is important to popularize innovative forms of providing new jobs to the population and create conditions. Studying the experience of developed countries, we can emphasize that remote employment is one of the modern and promising forms of providing new jobs to the population. The main advantage of home work is its flexibility. Employees have the opportunity to organize work remotely based on mutual agreement, regardless of the location of the enterprise.

In our opinion, remote employment is a form of employment in which the employer and employee are located in separate buildings and communicate through information and communication technologies.

The following types of remote employment can be distinguished:

- housework. It involves performing some tasks at home. An example of this is home economics;

- Remote employment is referred to in some literature as telebands or telecomputers. They work remotely. An employment contract is concluded between the employer and the employee;

- mobile remote employment. It can be done even without a personal computer or Internet connection. Examples include sales agents;

- freelancing, in which the employee performs labor activities and certain tasks without being registered as an employee of the enterprise.

Organization of freelancing and outsourcing (VRO) activities as a modern form of employment provision is one of the important measures in the development of the

digital economy in our republic."Freelancing" in English"free hire" as an actor, designer, programmer, journalist or free thinker and Outsourcing is an English word with "out" meaning "outside" and "sourcing" meaning "source" and refers to the connection of two different directions.. In the West, self-employed private doctors and lawyers are also considered freelancers. Freelance—is a very common trend lately. Uzbekistan also has more than 1500 freelancers registered on Russian and American freelance exchanges. Freelancing is not considered as a separate activity from individual entrepreneurship, therefore, a separate feature of legal regulation is not defined.

Summarizing the experience of foreign countries in regulating freelancing, the relationship between a freelancer and an employer can be formalized in several ways (Figure 2):

- as an individual based on a civil-legal contract;
- as an individual entrepreneur based on a civil-legal contract;
- through online freelance exchanges based on a tripartite agreement.

When some aspects of freelancing are legalized, they prevent informal employment, formalize their income and, especially when there are no jobs available in the area of residence, they can be formally employed remotely, realize their skills and have an income. allows.

Forming a legal basis for freelancing and accepting it as a separate type of employment will lead to a decrease in the unemployment rate. This, in turn, makes it possible to create an effective model of creating material wealth in the field of freelancing, to form and develop freelancers' exchanges, and to provide jobs to the unemployed and mainly young people in the regions.

The employment elasticity model is determined by the institutional structure of the labor market. Features of the institutional structure of the national labor market are manifested in strict rules and some shortcomings of the system that forces compliance with them.

2 - picture. Freelancing formation model in the labor market

Accordingly, the labor legislation of our republic has the following obstacles to the wide application of employment flexibility mechanisms in practice, including:

- unilateral termination of labor relations at the will of employers requires a long period of time and high costs for them;
- limited opportunities to introduce temporary labor contracts, especially in large and private enterprises, keeping a closed list of reasons that can serve as a basis for concluding fixed-term contracts;
- there are no opportunities to sign labor contracts as a part-time worker;
- Development of legal norms on the regulation of hired labor in the Labor Code or in a separate law.

The lack of legal regulation of the use of hired labor leads to the existence of economic and social risks for employers and workers.

Liberalization and differentiation of labor legislation should be carried out in harmony with the strengthening of information efforts. Information protection protects the rights of the employee as a mechanism to encourage compliance with the employment contract. In turn, the information system coordinates socio-economic relations by protecting the interests of employees and prevents conflicts between the participants of social and labor relations, and encourages the employer to fulfill the terms of the contract and follow the rules of procedure.

The increase in the institutional flexibility of the labor market is in two directions- it is desirable to implement the legislation on employment protection by liberalizing and strengthening labor relations enforcement.

The fact that the institutional structure of the labor market is based on strict procedures leads to an increase in the scale of structural and long-term unemployment

in the labor market. Accordingly, it is important to improve the legal-normative factors of the institutional flexibility structure aimed at improving the labor market regulation, the formation of informal norms and institutions, and the improvement of recommendations for determining and evaluating forms of their flexibility.

The stable condition of the modern labor market requires a sufficiently successful solution to the problems expected by all its subjects. Development of scientifically based conclusions and proposals on ensuring the flexibility of employment in the conditions of effective development of the labor market is an important goal of sociological research.

Busy with remote workregulatory and legal hujjatlar state, employer and employeearrange relations betweenit is appropriate to protect their interests and reflect their subordinatesis:

- e.g. regulation of the wages of the officially employed and wagesregulating the levy system;
- remote workersinterests and rightsto reflect;
- employers' obligations and rights, the effect on employees with remote workregulation of dogs;
- faqregulation of employers' obligations in emergency situations; remotey employed persons, their work activities and mehmechanisms for regulating nat results;
- regulation of relations with the trade union;
- regulation of relations with subjects of remote employment;
- state regulation of remote employmentdevelopment of standards;
- employer and employee taxa determination of the weighting procedure;
- remote workemployers in employment with hand a state that provides employee benefitsIt is appropriate to reflect the guarantees.

We distinguish the advantages and disadvantages of modern forms of employment. The advantage of modern forms of employment is the rational use of working time for both the employee and the employer. Due to this, the flexibility of the labor market is increasing, as each person chooses an employer for himself for a

short period of time and has a high level of competence, which leads to an increase in the employment rate of citizens, including those with disabilities, new jobs are created. ladi, the hiring and firing procedure will be simplified. Costs are reduced for businesses as they are able to retain the necessary workers in the event of a drop in employee productivity.

Modern forms of employment, such as freelance and remote employment, allow establishing labor relations with employers from any place without being limited by borders and long distances [6].

When selecting a freelancer, an employer focuses on work experience rather than appearance, age, gender, education, and presentation of completed work.

The main disadvantages of non-traditional forms of employment can be seen as the development of informality and unemployment, because labor relations are not always formalized, as a result of which there are risks that the employee will not be able to protect his rights in case of disputes.

Modern forms of employment lead to the emergence of independent professionals who are highly motivated and possess significant human and social capital. In this regard, they are important subjects of the modernization of the economy of our country, and the possibilities of using digital technologies for the implementation of their activities expand the prospects of personal development.

When some aspects of remote employment are legalized, informal employment will be prevented, income will be formalized and, especially when there is no job available in the area of residence, remote employment will be officially employed, they will be able to realize their abilities and have an income. will be created.

In the effective organization of remote employment, it is important to improve the labor legislation, improve the system of guarantees for remote workers, control tools and ensure communication and information security.

In the age of information, when choosing a modern form of employment, a person considers the workplace as a situation without looking at it as a lifelong choice. The main reason for this choice is to gain work experience in various fields, using educational and professional opportunities. Therefore, with the development of the digital economy, it is appropriate to prioritize the development of human capital. Implementation of qualitative changes in the employment sector, creation of high-performance jobs, technological growth, upgrading of equipment and it is necessary to develop new innovative areas of industry.

According to the results of the conducted scientific research, the following conclusions were drawn, including:

- providing one-time or temporary employment to the unemployed;
- implementation of the system of retraining those with secondary and secondary special education for traditional and modern occupations in short periods of time;
- creation of conditions for the development of employment of the unemployed, especially young people in need of employment, in traditional working professions and remote work;
- It is important to improve the institutional basis for reducing the informal employment of the population.

CONCLUSION

In order to prevent the expansion of the currently growing unemployment in our republic, social protection of unorganized youth, population in need of employment and the unemployed, retraining for traditional and modern labor professions, improvement of the organizational and economic basis of increasing the efficiency of their employment, informal on the basis of reduction of employment, optimization of the system of social guarantees and development of digital platforms, scientific and practical recommendations were developed on the improvement of the remote employment system focused on tripartite relations between the employer, online exchanges and employees.

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